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**Scientific and societal relevance and impact studies for
the CAIRT mission**

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**Q. Errera¹, P. Preusse², P. Raspollini³, P. Sellitto⁴,
M. Höpfner⁵, B.-M. Sinnhuber⁵**

¹**Royal Belgian Institute for Space Aeronomy (BIRA-IASB)**, *Ringlaan 3 Avenue Circulaire, 1180 Brussels, Belgium*

²**Forschungszentrum Jülich (FZJ)**, *Wilhelm-Johnen-Straße, 52428 Jülich, Germany*

³**National Research Council of Italy-Institute of Applied Physics "Nello Carrara"**, *via Madonna del Piano 10, 50019 Sesto Fiorentino, Firenze, Italy*

⁴**Laboratoire Interuniversitaire des Systèmes Atmosphériques (LISA)**, **Institut Pierre Simon Laplace (IPSL)**, **Université Paris Est Créteil (UPEC)**, France

⁵**Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT)**, *Hermann-von-Helmholtz-Platz 1, 76344 Eggenstein-Leopoldshafen, Germany*

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<p><i>Abstract</i></p> <p>This report reviews the scientific and societal relevance of the Earth Explorer 11 candidate mission CAIRT and identifies impact studies to demonstrate the scientific and societal benefits of the CAIRT mission. Past impact studies performed in support of the PREMIER and ALTIUS missions are reviewed and their applicability for CAIRT discussed, taking into account results published since then. Based on these findings, as well as results from CAIRT Phase 0/A studies, recommendations are formulated for possible future impact studies beyond Phase A.</p>		
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<i>Names of authors</i>		
Q. Errera, P. Preusse, P. Raspollini, P. Sellitto, M. Höpfner, B.-M. Sinnhuber		
<i>ESA Technical Officer</i> Alex Hoffmann Division Mission Science Division Directorate Directorate of Earth Observation Programmes	<i>ESA budget heading</i>	

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List of acronyms

ACE-FTS	Atmospheric Chemistry Experiment – Fourier Transform Spectrometer
ACT	ACross Track
AIRS	Atmospheric Infrared Sounder
ALT	ALong Track
ALTIUS	Atmospheric Limb Tracker for the Investigation of the Upcoming Stratosphere
AK	Averaging Kernel
APARC	Atmosphere And their Role in Climate (formely SPARC)
BASCOE	Belgian Assimilation System for Chemical Observations
CAIRT	Changing Atmosphere Infra-Red Tomography explorer
CAMS	Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service
CFC	Chloro Fluoro Carbon
CRISTA	CRyogenic Infrared Spectrometers and Telescopes for the Atmosphere
DA	Data Assimilation
ECMWF	European Centre for Medium range Weather Forecast
EnKF	Ensemble Kalman Filter
HIRDLS	High Resolution Dynamics Limb Sounder
GPS/GNSS-RO	GPS/GNSS – Radio Occultation
MIAP	Mission Impact Assessment Plan
MIPAS	Michelson Interferometer for Passive Atmospheric Sounding
MLS	Microwave Limb Souder
MLT	Mesosphere Lower Thermosphere
MO	Mission Objective of CAIRT
NRT	Near Real Time
OSSE	Observing System Simulation Experiment
PerReC	CAIRT Performance and Requirement Consolidation study
SABER	Sounding of the Atmosphere using Broadband Emission Radiometry
SAGE	Stratospheric Aerosol and Gas Experiment
SciReC	CAIRT Scientific and Requirement Consolidation study
SO	Scientific Objective of CAIRT
SPARC	Stratosphere-troposphere And their Role in Climate (now APARC)
STE	Stratosphere-Troposphere Exchange
TDS-P	Test Data Set-Product
UTLS	Upper Troposphere Lower Stratosphere
UTTC	Ultra Thin Tropical tropopause Cloud
WP	Work Package (of PerReC if no other project mentioned)

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1 Introduction

An essential input to the Report for Mission Selection (RfMS) is evidence that the successful EE11 mission candidate has a high potential for advancing science and that the candidate can lead to excellent societal benefits. In addition, SRL-5 requires evidence of user interest and innovative scientific application(s) of foreseen mission outputs, including a first evaluation of mission data in applications.

The Performance and Requirement Consolidation study (PerReC) therefore aims at effectively communicating how the mission differs from other observing systems and demonstrating how it provides novel measurements and data products of high scientific and societal value beyond present capabilities.

The objectives of this technical note are then:

1. To collect and assemble relevant information substantiating clear need of CAIRT data for the scientific community. This is done in Sect. 2.
2. To collect and assemble relevant information substantiating clear benefit of CAIRT data in societal applications. This is done in Sect. 3.
3. Review case and/or impact studies done for other missions and summarize reliable finding that remains applicable for the CAIRT mission. This is done in Sect. 0.
4. Guide the formulation of new impact studies to achieve during Phase A or beyond. This is done in Sect. 5.

2 CAIRT Data for the Scientific Community

CAIRT observations of temperature and composition from the free troposphere to the lower thermosphere will be exploited by many communities to advance our understanding of atmospheric processes and changes in vertical coupling, transport, and circulation (globally and regionally). The targeted mission lifetime of five years or more enables the observation of the causes and consequences of internal and forced climate variability throughout the atmosphere, including links to the QBO, sudden stratospheric warmings, El Niño Southern Oscillation, solar variability, forest fires and volcanic eruptions.

The unique capability of CAIRT to resolve small-scale structures means that the characterization and understanding of underlying processes (gravity waves, mixing, NO_x production in the upper atmosphere, injection of water and aerosols into the stratosphere) and their impact on the larger-scale circulation and composition is possible. Ultimately, CAIRT data will be used to improve NWP, (chemistry)-climate, upper atmosphere, and Earth system models. CAIRT data exploitation will include the examination of zonal averages and of more complex four-dimensional, self-consistent, and gridded L3 products.

Data Exploitation

With the imminent loss of current limb satellite instruments, and uncertain plans for their continuation, there will be a strong uptake of CAIRT data by the **limb sounding community**. Grand advancements from the use of limb sounding data to date have been plentiful. Recent examples include the observed MLT cooling due to CO₂ emissions (Mlynczak et al., 2022), confirming a fundamental climate change prediction (Solomon et al., 2019). Another example is the largest-ever observed injection of H₂O into the stratosphere by the Hunga Tonga-Hunga Ha'apai volcanic eruption in 2022, observed by Aura/MLS (Millán et al., 2022). The radiative forcing from the excess H₂O may outweigh the reflection of solar radiation by sulfate aerosols, making the Hunga Tonga-Hunga Ha'apai potentially the first eruption to warm rather than cool the surface (Jenkins et al., 2023; P. Sellitto et al., 2022). Other examples are the never before observed 2015/2016 and 2019/2020 QBO disruptions, and the associated changes in H₂O, O₃, and other trace gases. Such QBO disruptions are expected to increase with climate change (Anstey et al., 2021). There has also been a record injection of biomass burning products and carbon monoxide into the lower stratosphere after the Australian black summer in 2019/2020 (Khaykin et al., 2020) that induced strong and unexplained repartitioning in the chlorine-containing gases (Santee et al., 2022) and stratospheric ozone depletion (Solomon et al., 2023). As the frequency and intensity of wildfires are expected to increase (Dowdy et al., 2019), as well as extreme pyrocumulonimbus (pyroCb) events (Peterson et al., 2025), they are now a significant contributor to the UTLS composition. **Given all this, CAIRT will expand our capability to observe and understand the impact of such events, but also to discover and explore the unexpected.**

CAIRT data will answer outstanding questions in the **gravity wave community**. Our current understanding of atmospheric gravity waves comes from observations made by the HIRDLS, CRISTA, SABER, GPS-RO and AIRS instruments. CAIRT will provide a much better quantitative view of gravity waves (and of their momentum flux, phase speed, and wavelength distribution and direction) as well as a reliable estimate of gravity wave drag which are necessary to improve atmospheric models.

CAIRT data will be used by the **upper atmosphere and space weather community** to address key questions of solar-terrestrial and climate coupling, identified by the International Science Council's Scientific Committee on Solar-Terrestrial Physics (SCOSTEP) and its current science program PRESTO (Predictability of the Solar-Terrestrial Coupling, Daglis et al., 2021). These include a better understanding of the lower

thermosphere response to forcings from above and below; the impact of waves on the middle and upper atmosphere; the chemical and dynamical response to energetic particle precipitation; the vertical coupling of the lower and upper atmosphere; and of how the atmospheric response to the variable solar forcing may be affected by, and interacts with, increasing greenhouse gases and stratospheric ozone recovery from CFC reduction.

CAIRT data will be highly valuable for the **upper troposphere – stratosphere (UTS) community** for WMO/UNEP assessments of the state of the ozone layer and the success of the Montreal Protocol. CAIRT observations will enable the continuation of merged ozone datasets used in the World Climate Research Programme’s Atmosphere Processes And their Role in Climate activities ([APARC/IO3C/GAW](#)) and of other key constituents that are crucial for the understanding of the ozone layer. CAIRT observations of climate forcers like stratospheric water vapour and aerosols will be extremely useful to evaluate their impact on the UTS. CAIRT sulfur observations will enable the differentiation between aerosols injected by volcanic eruptions compared to other sources (wildfires or air pollution lofted within the monsoon systems), all relevant to the [IPCC](#), ESA’s Climate Change Initiative on water vapour and aerosols and the APARC/SSiRC (Stratospheric Sulphur and its Role on Climate) activity.

CAIRT tropospheric ozone data, in combination with nadir observations will be exploited for the evaluation of long-term trends in tropospheric ozone, where ozone is an important greenhouse gas and affects air quality. Together with other CAIRT atmospheric composition data obtained in the free and upper troposphere such as methane, water vapour, HCN or PAN, this will be used by the **atmospheric chemistry community** to evaluate chemical processes in these regions.

The Importance of CAIRT for Atmospheric and Earth System Models

Due to its large number of geophysical observations, CAIRT data will be used *to provide initial conditions for, to develop, assess, and to validate* a range of models, including NWP, air quality, (chemistry)-climate, and space weather models. Some examples are provided below.

Near-real-time (NRT) assimilation of CAIRT data will improve **initial conditions**, thus providing better weather and air quality forecasts, such as at ECMWF and the Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service (CAMS). CAIRT data will also contribute to meteorological and chemical **reanalyses** produced by these centres. The lack of limb sounding O₃ profiles in the CAMS data assimilation system is known to induce degradation in its analyses and forecasts (Flemming et al., 2011), while the necessity for water vapour observations in the stratosphere for better NWP is recognized at ECMWF (Polichtchouk et al., 2021). CAIRT will also better quantify troposphere and middle atmosphere trace gases from data fusion of limb-nadir observations relevant for climate monitoring. For example, the bias found in the stratospheric representation of CAMS CH₄ and N₂O could be eliminated using NRT profiles of these gases (Verma et al., 2017). CAIRT will further provide initial conditions for whole-atmosphere prediction systems with space weather applications for which limited global observations are currently available, such as the NCAR’s WACCM-X+DART (Pedatella et al., 2019). CAIRT data can also be used by NWP centres to derive online bias correction, as is currently done operationally at ECMWF when producing operational analyses (Laloyaux et al., 2020).

CAIRT will help to **diagnose the Brewer-Dobson** circulation in (chemistry)-climate models and meteorological (re)-analyses. Currently, there is a large contradiction in age-of-air estimates and trends between in-situ observations, models, and meteorological reanalyses (Butchart, 2014; Chabrilat et al., 2018). CAIRT observations (including of age-of-air) will be used to assess model representation of horizontal mixing and residual vertical transport which is relevant for many SPARC activities. CAIRT ozone profiles will also help to

diagnose stratosphere to troposphere transport, a need recognized within SPARC and the International Global Atmospheric Chemistry (IGAC) programme.

CAIRT **gravity wave** (GW) observations will provide constraints and physical understanding on their sources, propagation, and dissipation which will be used to evaluate and improve gravity wave representation by km-scale models that resolve them explicitly and by models using gravity wave parameterizations (Plougonven et al., 2020; Polichtchouk et al., 2023). An accurate representation of gravity waves in models will improve our understanding of the middle-atmosphere circulation and provide better weather forecasts. This need fits within the framework of the World Climate Research Programme's (WCRP) Working Group on Numerical Experimentation ([WGNE](#)), SPARC, and the European km-scale global modelling projects Destination Earth ([DestinE](#)).

CAIRT data will be used by **upper atmosphere and space weather models**. Temperature and chemical composition trends from these models, and the coupling between space and surface weather is currently poorly understood (Szeląg et al., 2022). In the upper atmosphere, important observables of energy budget, dynamics, chemistry, transport, and coupling include H₂O, CO, CH₄, O₃, NO, NO₂ and temperature (see [ESA MesosphEO](#) project), all measured by CAIRT. CAIRT data will thus constitute a benchmark for the representation of mesosphere-stratosphere coupling in models, enabling a well-constrained quantification of space-weather-driven impacts on natural climate variability. CAIRT NO_x observations will provide stringent constraints for energetic particle-induced atmospheric ionization, and related chemical upper boundary constraints. Both are part of the latest Coupled Model Intercomparison Project (CMIP) solar forcing recommendations for chemistry-climate models (Matthes et al., 2017).

CAIRT data will be used to derive accurate **trace gas and aerosol climatology** to validate climate projections. For example, stratospheric sulfate aerosols have the potential to directly decrease surface temperatures by backscattering parts of the incoming solar radiation. Estimates of the amount of stratospheric aerosol and their evolution are therefore important for climate modelling studies. CAIRT data will also help to improve linearized ozone parametrisation that includes radiative feedback, currently used at ECMWF (Williams et al., 2021). Such parameterizations rely on ozone observations and need to be continuously refined to reflect e.g., ozone trends and new understanding of the ozone chemistry.

3 CAIRT Data for Societal Applications

In addition to its scientific uses outlined in Sect. 2, CAIRT data will fill a major gap in monitoring of essential climate variables (WMO (GCOS-245), 2022), in support to international treaties like the Paris Agreement as well as the Parties of the Montreal Protocol. CAIRT data will be crucial for **monitoring possible future deliberate stratospheric aerosol injection as part of proposed geoengineering schemes**, together with any potential adverse effects on the ozone layer.

The use of CAIRT data to improve NWP and air quality forecasts offers great societal benefits. CAIRT products could also be used to inform aviation about risks of volcanic ash (Griessbach et al., 2014). CAIRT gravity-wave observations may inform aviation of clear-air-turbulence, including High Altitude Platform Systems in the stratosphere. CAIRT composition data will further be useful for assessing the climate impact of aviation, high-altitude and suborbital flights, under scenarios of increased spacefaring. There is a growing concern that gases and particulates emitted by rockets into the middle atmosphere or emitted by satellite demise can alter the stratospheric composition and damage the protective ozone layer (Brown et al., 2023; Ferreira et al., 2024; Murphy et al., 2023).

Finally, CAIRT data will also bring a better physical understanding of how the upper thermosphere continues to change with increases in CO₂. The availability of temperature in the MLT allows estimating the contraction of the thermosphere and to estimate the decreasing in thermospheric density.

The projected further cooling and contraction of the upper atmosphere can have several technical and socio-economic impacts, such as the reduction of drag on satellites and space debris in the low orbits. While the former is beneficial for satellite mission lifetime, the latter poses greater risks of further accumulation of space debris in Low Earth Orbit, leading to an increase of on-orbit collisions, due to a reduced debris removal efficacy (Lewis et al., 2011).

Space debris models have been created to investigate the long-term evolution of the debris environment. The model requires the estimation of the atmospheric density at high altitude (up to about 700 km) to evaluate the drag effect. Hence, they require assumptions on the scenario of CO₂ increase and constraints on temperature evolution. It has been proven with models (Brown et al., 2021) that limiting warming to the 1.5°C target of the Paris Agreement will still result in a 27% to 30% reduction in density in 2100 relative to the year 2000 at 400 km, with orbital lifetimes increasing by around 30% as a result. Even under the low CO₂ emissions (RCP2.6 scenarios), the drop in neutral density will have a substantial impact on LEO object orbital lifetimes, as well as the debris environment within this region.

The use of a correct decreasing thermospheric density trend is crucial for the correct forecast of these models because simulations can run for many decades, even centuries into the future, over which secular density trends will have an important cumulative effect.

4 Past Case and/or Impact Studies Relevant for the CAIRT Mission

This section reviews existing cases and/or impact studies that have been done for the past missions PREMIER (which was not selected) and ALTIUS (which will be launched at the end of 2026). These case and/or impact studies are:

1. PREMIER Observation of Gravity Waves from Space (Preusse et al., 2012b)
2. PREMIER Quantification of Atmospheric Pollution and Climate Aspects (Riese et al., 2012, 2011)
3. PREMIER Characterisation of Particulates in the Upper Troposphere / Lower Stratosphere (Griessbach et al., 2018a)
4. ALTIUS Observing System Simulation Experiment on Stratospheric Ozone (Errera et al., 2021)

4.1 PREMIER Observation of Gravity Waves from Space

This study was commissioned by ESA following selection of PREMIER by ESA's PB-EO in February 2009 for feasibility studies (Phase A) as one of three candidate missions for Earth Explorer-7. The purpose of the study was to demonstrate that an infrared limb imager as to be used in the PREMIER mission is able to quantify gravity wave (GW) momentum flux at an accuracy sufficient to solve open scientific questions in this field. In particular, it shall be demonstrated that PREMIER can provide unprecedented information on the global momentum budget as well as on various GW processes and that comparable information cannot be obtained by any other measurement technique which could be realized by current technology.

The study, presented in Preusse et al. (2012), was extensive in scope and organized in the following tasks

1. Literature study and definition of requirements
2. Selection of numerical models and scenarios
3. PREMIER 2D temperature retrieval
4. Tools for GW isolation and identification
5. Gravity wave ray tracing
6. Determination and assessment of GW momentum flux (GWMF)
7. Scientific interpretation by ray tracing
8. Validation
9. Conclusions and recommendations

The study provides a successful proof of concept. The inferred level of accuracy for zonal mean GWMF matches to the requirements, which are needed for a significant scientific progress in the field. The ray-tracing task further demonstrates the huge potential of such an unprecedented and unparalleled data set for scientific investigations. However, the study also made evident that substantial work had to be still done for implementing a retrieval for a space-borne limb imager:

Retrievals

- Complete processing of four weeks of ECMWF scenario data with the JURASSIC-1 code used at the time would have required a significant amount of computer time far beyond NRT requirements. Further optimization of the tomographic retrieval system was therefore identified as a prerequisite to continuously process real data at a later stage. *Several such optimizations were under development at FZJ since then (Ungermann, 2012, 2011). During CAIRT Phase0/A studies it was shown that the current version of JURASSIC-2 is capable of producing CAIRT data in NRT.*

- Regularization parameters for the retrieval were further optimized to find the best trade-off between spatial resolution and retrieval noise. It needs to be considered that regularization also provides stability for the numerical inversion process.
- The selection of spectral micro-windows was based on 1D linear error simulations. 2D error analysis carried out during the course of the PREMIER GW study indicated that the 1D error estimates cannot be transferred to 2D. Further attention should be given to 2D retrieval tests with different micro-window settings.

Detrending

A space-time spectral analysis needs to be employed to subtract the background atmosphere for real observations. To proof the methodology requires the generation of a fully time-dependent test data set.

Validation and Scientific Interpretation

More steps in the direction of the assimilation of different measurement techniques into a mesoscale model should be taken. This could be tested in observing system simulation experiments (OSSEs) as well as for real campaigns. For instance, the MAARSY radar and the GLORIA airborne limb imager have the potential to provide 3D wind (MAARSY) and temperature (GLORIA) fields suited for test evaluations.

4.2 PREMIER Quantification of Atmospheric Pollution and Climate Aspects

The primary aim of this study was to explore the potential impact of PREMIER data on the understanding of various atmospheric processes that are crucial for air quality, climate change, and their interactions. The study was divided into four key tasks. The findings from all four tasks (presented in Riese et al., 2011 and summarized in Riese et al., 2012) underscore the significant potential impact of the PREMIER mission. A summary of the key results is as follows.

4.2.1 Task-1: Quantifying the impact of biomass burning (BB) on atmospheric composition in the UTLS (Upper Troposphere/Lower Stratosphere) and its effects on the atmospheric radiation balance.

Task-1 demonstrated that biomass burning plays a significant role in overall atmospheric radiative forcing (RF). PREMIER's high spatial and temporal resolution allows detecting and analysing plumes of BB emissions in the UTLS, offering more detailed information than current space-based instruments. The global radiative forcing from biomass burning is significant, with most of the impact occurring over a longer timescale (e.g., from ozone production after VOC oxidation). Overall, the study highlights how PREMIER can improve our understanding of intense fires and, in particular, pyro-convective events. Even if more studies have been realized since Riese et al., 2012, about pyro-convective events and the generation of pyro-cumulonimbus (pyro-Cbs) clouds, the understanding of these extreme fire events is far from complete. Nevertheless, it is now well established that: (1) extreme fires and pyro-Cb events are increasing in frequency (Wilmot et al., 2022), and (2) their impact on the trace gas distribution, atmospheric chemistry and radiative forcing are important and long-lasting (Khaykin et al., 2020; Pasquale Sellitto et al., 2022) The high spatial and temporal resolution of PREMIER are well adapted to characterize pyro-Cbs formation and their evolution, which are processes that occur at relatively small spatiotemporal scales, using measurements of fire tracers. Chemical impacts can also be monitored, using observations of carbon and sulphur-containing gaseous and particulate species.

4.2.2 **Task-2:** *Quantifying the transport processes involved in stratosphere-troposphere exchange at high spatial resolution and examining the effect of resolution on calculated radiative forcing patterns.*

Task-2 showed that PREMIER could reduce uncertainties in transport schemes (e.g., mixing), which significantly affect globally averaged radiative forcing of water vapour and ozone. This capability arises from PREMIER's ability to resolve small-scale structures, such as filaments, that are influenced by mixing processes, unlike limb sounders like MIPAS.

Furthermore, results from Task-2, along with other recent studies, revealed that changes in trace gas distributions in the UTLS (and the related changes in radiative forcing) will feedback into the troposphere, thus influencing climate change. In particular, parameters like surface temperature and precipitation at high latitudes are highly sensitive to variations in the UTLS. PREMIER will help bridge gaps in our understanding of the UTLS's interaction with climate change, necessary to evaluate atmospheric and chemistry-climate models.

4.2.3 **Task-3:** *Demonstrating the added value of PREMIER data to data assimilation systems used in numerical weather prediction and environmental forecasting.*

Task-3 demonstrated that PREMIER data can provide valuable contributions across several research areas where the assimilation of remote-sensing data is crucial for output quality. In WP3100, simulated observations from PREMIER, such as temperature, water vapour, and ozone data, were assimilated into NWP system, revealing substantial improvements as compared to MLS in analyses and forecasts, especially for ozone and water vapour in the troposphere and UTLS.

Joined assimilation of ozone MIPAS limb profiles and IASI nadir total columns serving as proxies for PREMIER have been assimilated by the air quality forecast model MOCAGE (WP3200). It reveals that limb data effectively captured ozone patterns in the UTLS, improving the realism of modelled tropospheric structures. However, the study faced challenges due to the low frequency of relevant events and potential biases in IASI retrievals, impacting the reliability of some skill scores. Despite these challenges, the study suggested that a combination of nadir and limb data, or PREMIER data, would enhance the accuracy of ozone assessments, with benefits for air quality predictions.

In that study, only two months over four have been analyses, where only ozonesonde at Payerne were used for the evaluation. Several papers have discussed assimilation of MLS to analyse stratosphere-troposphere ozone exchange (Barré et al., 2012) or joint assimilation of MLS and IASI to constrain stratospheric and tropospheric ozone (Barré et al., 2014; Emili et al., 2014). While these studies highlighted that MLS profiles or MLS+IASI added values to constrain the UTLS and the troposphere, none of these studies quantified how MLS or MLS+IASI remove the ozone bias in the troposphere.

Sensitivity study using PREMIER profiles to constrain tropospheric methane was also carried out in this Task 3 (WP3300). It reveals that PREMIER profiles of methane down to 150 hPa would capture a large part of the variability in methane total column mixing ratio (CMR) due to stratospheric transport, mixing and chemistry, tropopause height variations, and stratosphere-troposphere exchange. However observations down to 500 hPa would be much better because also capturing the variability caused by convection and long-range transport in the upper troposphere. It is recommended to investigate if the combination of IASI CH₄ nadir observations and PREMIER CH₄ limb profiles could provide the required observational constraints in the UTLS region on the total CMR variations.

4.2.4 **Task-4:** *Contributing to the validation of chemistry-climate models (CCMs).*

Task-4 demonstrated that PREMIER could significantly enhance the validation of CCMs, particularly in the UTLS region, where atmospheric observations are limited and dynamic variability often introduces large errors in climatology compilation. PREMIER's measurements would help define climatological mean variables without the need for addressing sampling biases and would provide insights into natural variability at shorter time and spatial scales. The high spatial and temporal resolution of PREMIER data is essential for developing process-oriented diagnostics, which are crucial for successful CCM validation and a deeper understanding of the physical and chemical processes governing tracer distributions in the UTLS. Specifically, PREMIER's measurements could help investigate the relationship between the strength of the Brewer-Dobson circulation and its impact on vertical ozone distribution across different time and spatial scales, and assess associated variability.

4.2.5 *Conclusions*

1. PREMIER can quantify key processes controlling global atmospheric composition (e.g., transport, mixing, radiative forcing) in the mid/upper troposphere and lower stratosphere (5–25 km), a region critical for climate change.
2. PREMIER provides added value for the validation of chemistry-climate models (CCMs) and data assimilation systems used in numerical weather prediction (NWP).

4.3 *PREMIER Characterisation of Particulates in the Upper Troposphere / Lower Stratosphere*

Although clouds and aerosols were not initially considered retrieval targets of PREMIER, Griessbach et al. (2018) has highlighted the potential of the infrared limb sounding instrument (IRLS), a key component of PREMIER, to detect particles in the UTLS. This study was organized into four main tasks:

1. Defining scientific and operational objectives
2. Creating representative test cases
3. Investigating the IRLS sensitivity to clouds and aerosols and its spatial detection capabilities
4. Assessing the microphysical retrieval capabilities of IRLS

Task 1 summarized the key technical specifications of the PREMIER IRLS and reviewed the current understanding of UTLS ice clouds, aerosols, and polar stratospheric clouds (PSCs). It also outlined specific scientific and operational goals for measuring cirrus clouds, aerosols, and PSCs.

Task 2 involved creating representative test cases to evaluate the IRLS's ability to measure aerosols and clouds. Six test cases were generated:

1. First, more than 6800 1D scenarios accounting for realistic particle size and number concentrations for ice clouds, sulfate aerosols, and spherical and non-spherical volcanic ash particles is simulated. It is used to derive information on IRLS detection sensitivity, estimation of altitude information accuracy, development of particle classification type algorithm, and the development of a particle size and extinction retrieval.
2. The second test case consists of two case studies of volcanic plumes, one composed of volcanic ash and the other composed of sulfate aerosols. Here complex 2D spatial structures of the plumes are

- the key property. This case is used to demonstrate the spatial (vertical and horizontal) detection capabilities and to test the classification and retrieval schemes on realistic volcanic plume structures.
3. For the third test case CALIOP cloud measurements and high resolved CLaMSIce simulations were used to generate realistic and complex 3D ice clouds. This test case was used to evaluate the spatial (horizontal and vertical) 3-D detection capabilities.
 4. The fourth test case contains a 2D ultra thin tropical tropopause cloud (UTTC) based on in-situ measurement data. It is used to explore the detection capabilities close to the detection limit, vertical detection capabilities for multilayer structures, and the impact of underlying clouds as a source of uncertainty.
 5. The fifth test case contains the same UTTC as the fourth test case, but with 1D geometry and varying ice-water content and particle sizes that cover the range from optically thin to thick. This test case is used to develop and test a cirrus cloud microphysical retrieval, to explore the detection sensitivity towards ice, and characterize cloud top altitude under the condition of underlying thick ice clouds.
 6. The sixth test case contains 12 different PSC scenarios based on in-situ balloon measurements. These scenarios were used to derive PSC detection sensitivities, develop a PSC particle classification algorithm, develop a PSC microphysical retrieval, and to test the sensitivity of the methods towards non-spherical PSC particles.

Not considered, but could be in future work are the (i) optimization of radiative transfer simulations for altitudes below 10km with a particular focus on water vapour and (ii) simulations for other aerosol types upon availability of high spectral resolution IR refractive index data could.

Task 3 analysed the spatial and spectral detection capabilities of IRLS, compared to MIPAS, using different detection methods. Results showed that IRLS and MIPAS have similar spectral detection but that IRLS had significantly better spatial detection than MIPAS, offering improved spatial sampling, global coverage, and temporal resolution compared to other space-based aerosol measurements. IRLS also demonstrated a sensitivity range that fills a gap between UV/VIS limb and IR nadir measurements, with lower detection limits better than those of SAGE II and upper limits above the thresholds of IR nadir instruments. *This gap covers the range where UTTC can be detected, as also proven by the analysis of the middle infrared limb instrument CRISTA-2 characterized by a vertical resolution comparable with CAIRT one. The radiative effect of UTCC has been estimated by (Spang et al., 2024).*

Task 4 focused on classifying aerosols, ice clouds, and PSCs, and retrieving microphysical properties with IRLS. It was found that, similar to IR nadir measurements, volcanic ash can be distinguished from ice clouds. Additionally, IRLS was sensitive to sulfate aerosols and PSCs, which were also classifiable. Techniques were developed to estimate ice water content, particle concentration, extinction, and particle size, even for optically thin clouds, PSCs, and aerosols viewed in the limb direction.

Overall, this study demonstrates that the IRLS instrument has the capability to provide detailed information on particles in the UTLS, such as thin cirrus clouds, aerosols, and PSCs, which are not detectable by many existing and upcoming atmospheric sounding instruments. *By exploiting the spatial overlap of measurements it is possible to more precisely detect the location of (optically thin) clouds (Ungermann et al., 2020).*

The study also suggests future work, in particular:

- To include additional particle types than those considered in the classification method.
- To study various effects of particle properties in the retrieval not considered here (retrieval with/without scattering, test refractive index assumption, impact of underlying clouds).

- To use information from the PSC classification as a priori knowledge for the retrieval
- To use information from multiple wavelengths to derive more information on the size and composition of PSCs
- To use joint IRLS and IR nadir retrieval to estimate impact on microphysical parameters
- To quantify capabilities to retrieve trace-gas concentration profiles from PSC/aerosol/cirrus affected spectra

All results found for IRLS can be directly applied also to CAIRT. The only difference between IRLS and CAIRT, in the altitude range of interest for the clouds, is that for IRLS a slightly better vertical resolution was assumed than for CAIRT. This should only slightly reduce the performances of CAIRT in resolving in altitude the shape of the clouds.

4.4 ALTIUS Observing System Simulation Experiment on Stratospheric Ozone

ALTIUS (Atmospheric Limb Tracker for the Investigation of the Upcoming Stratosphere) is the upcoming stratospheric ozone monitoring limb sounder from ESA's Earth Watch programme. Measuring in the ultraviolet– visible–near-infrared (UV–VIS–NIR) spectral regions, ALTIUS will retrieve vertical profiles of ozone, aerosol extinction coefficients, nitrogen dioxide and other trace gases from the upper troposphere to the mesosphere. In order to maximize the geographical coverage, the instrument will observe limb-scattered solar light during daytime (i.e. bright limb observations), solar occultations at the terminator and stellar/lunar/planetary occultations during nighttime. (Errera et al., 2021) evaluates the constraint of ALTIUS ozone profiles on modelled stratospheric ozone by means of an observing system simulation experiment (OSSE). In this effort, a reference atmosphere has been built and used to generate ALTIUS ozone profiles, along with an instrument simulator. These profiles are then assimilated to provide ozone analyses. A good agreement is found between the analyses and the reference atmosphere in the stratosphere and in the extratropical upper troposphere. **In the tropical upper troposphere, the assimilation of ozone profiles does not completely eliminate the bias with respect to the reference atmosphere.** The impacts of the different modes of observations have also been evaluated, showing that all of them are necessary to constrain ozone during polar winters where solar/stellar occultations are the most important during the polar night and bright limb data are the most important during the development of the ozone hole in the polar spring.

The ALTIUS study focused on the upper troposphere and stratosphere, results below 300 hPa were not presented or discussed. The study also showed that ALTIUS has a lower constraint on ozone than MLS in the UTLS, making ALTIUS observation not suited to diagnose ozone stratosphere to troposphere exchange. Results are thus not directly applicable for CAIRT.

5 Recommendations for future CAIRT impact studies beyond Phase A

Based on results achieved during CAIRT Phase 0 and Phase A, as well as relevant impact studies for other or previous missions, we summarize here recommendations for future impact studies (beyond Phase A) to demonstrate the impact of CAIRT observations for science and society. These recommendations are grouped according to CAIRT Science Objectives and Application Objectives, as defined in the CAIRT Report for Mission Selection. Priority should be given to studies that quantify the impact and added value achieved with CAIRT data.

SO-1 Diagnose the changing atmospheric *circulation* between the upper troposphere and the lower thermosphere, through observations of *temperature, long-lived trace gases* and derived *age-of-air*, from the global scale down to spatial scales associated with mixing and exchange processes.

Changes in the strength of the large-scale meridional circulation in the middle atmosphere (e.g. the Brewer-Dobson circulation) will have profound consequences on many aspects of atmospheric composition, dynamics and climate. Age-of-air is one powerful often-used diagnostic to quantify circulation aspects.

The studies conducted during CAIRT Phase A confirmed that age-of-air can be retrieved from CAIRT observations with a total error consistent with requirements (Voet et al., 2025). It was shown that age-of-air from CAIRT can significantly improve existing uncertainties in models (Section 7.4.1 in RfMS). This study, together with (Voet et al., 2025) will show quantitatively the impact of CAIRT measurements in diagnosing middle atmosphere circulation through age-of-air. We thus hope that this study can be published in the peer reviewed literature. What remains to be shown is how the concept of age-of-air can be extended to altitudes above the lower and middle stratosphere, ideally in a unified framework together with circulation diagnostics like CO and CH₄ as used in studies of descent of air in the mesosphere (e.g., Funke et al., 2014; von Clarmann et al., 2021). We recommend this to be investigated in future studies beyond CAIRT Phase A. This would also be useful beyond CAIRT to develop a consistent framework for the concept of age-of-air throughout the middle atmosphere.

Beside age-of-air observations, CAIRT observations of long-lived chemical species provide useful datasets to diagnose and constrain circulation in models. The Ensemble Kalman Filter (EnKF) data assimilation method uses correlations between model forecasts and observations to deliver an analysis increment allowing adjusting model initial conditions for the new forecast. In general, model variables are updated using similar observational variables (e.g. model ozone is updated thanks to ozone observations). However, the use of observations of one or several variables to constrain another model variable has never been tried in EnKF. For example, could – and to what extent – CAIRT observations of SF₆, CH₄, N₂O, CFC-11, CFC-12, HCFC-22, CO and H₂O could be used to constrain modelled age-of-air? This could be answered by numerical experiments where CAIRT observations are simulated using one model then assimilated with another model.

Mixing is an important part of the large-scale circulation. Work in support of the PREMIER mission (Riese et al., 2011); (Riese et al., 2012) have shown that the improved spatial resolution of infra-red limb imaging compared to other observations can help to better constrain mixing parametrizations in models with affecting the distribution of radiatively active gases (in particular O₃, H₂O and CH₄) with consequences for radiative forcing of surface climate (Riese et al., 2012). These results are specifically relevant for the CLAMS model, which – unlike most other models – have an explicit treatment of mixing. It is less clear how these results can be transferred to other models and how much quantitatively CAIRT observations would add compared to, e.g., many years of observations from limb sounders like MIPAS or MLS.

SO-2 Quantify the contribution of *gravity waves* to the driving of the middle atmospheric circulation, identify their *sources* and investigate their *propagation* and *dissipation*, through observations of gravity waves between the lower stratosphere and the mesosphere, and at scales relevant for circulation change.

Gravity waves are still one of the largest source of uncertainties in atmospheric models. The potential to improve our understanding of gravity waves through infra-red limb imaging was investigated in great detail in support of the PREMIER mission (Preusse et al., 2012a) and during Phase 0 and Phase A of the CAIRT mission. These studies showed quantitatively how information on sources, propagation and dissipation of gravity waves, as well as the associated drag on the circulation, can be improved by infra-red limb imaging (Rhode et al., 2024).

Previous improvement in gravity wave parametrizations in atmospheric models was largely the result of improved observations of gravity waves. In this respect, it would be beneficial showing quantitatively in atmospheric models how improvements in gravity wave parametrizations, as expected from CAIRT observations, could lead to improved model predictions and projections. See also AO-3 below.

To our knowledge very few estimates of errors for GW parameters exist and they are mainly on the ensemble means. Uncertainties of single-wave GW parameters have been quantified in PerReC for a first time. The method uses Monte-Carlo simulations of combined L2a/L2b retrievals, is accordingly costly and relies in its current implementation on some truth knowledge. Determination of wave parameters in a few-wave decomposition is a highly non-linear problem. Solving this via Monte Carlo simulations is a safe but costly method to determine whether solutions are stable and how much they scatter as a consequence of noise. In principle, one could imagine that this could also be determined via the topology of the chi-square function (optimization function) in spectral space. This would be an investment to any 3D observation of GWs from space.

SO-3 Investigate *upper atmospheric coupling* and concomitant regional surface climate variability associated with transient solar events and space weather through the *downward flux of reactive nitrogen (NO_y)* from the thermosphere, and its impacts on stratospheric ozone.

Studies during CAIRT Phase 0 and Phase A showed how CAIRT data can be used to quantify the flux of reactive nitrogen (NO_y) from the MLT region into the stratosphere (Section 7.2.3 in CAIRT RfA; Section 7.4.3 in CAIRT RfMS). Several previous modelling studies have investigated the concomitant regional surface climate variability associated with transient solar events and space weather through the downward flux of reactive nitrogen from the thermosphere, as well as its impacts on stratospheric ozone. One of the largest uncertainties in previous modelling studies was the treatment of gravity waves (Martínez-Andradas et al., 2025), which drive the descent of reactive nitrogen from the MLT regions down into the middle atmosphere. The impact study during CAIRT Phase A employed model simulations of WACCM-X with different gravity wave treatments to investigate the coupling between gravity wave driving and the descent of NO_y into the stratosphere (Section 7.4.3 in CAIRT RfMS).

CAIRT temperature observations in the MLT region may provide a continuity of the SABER observations over the previous decades. In this respect it would be highly beneficial to investigate the impact of CAIRT observations on constraining the MLT regions in models by OSSEs assimilating CAIRT temperature observations into upper-atmosphere models (such as WACCM-X or ICON in upper-atmosphere configuration).

SO-4 Quantify *lower atmospheric coupling* associated with the lofting or injection of natural and anthropogenic plumes of *pollutants and aerosol precursors* into the upper troposphere and stratosphere, their impacts on composition, and their crucial role for climate forcing and feedbacks.

A comprehensive investigation of the added value of infra-red limb imaging to characterize particulates (aerosols, clouds) in the UTLS region has been provided by (Griessbach et al., 2018b) in support of the PREMIER mission concept. Studies during CAIRT Phase 0 and Phase A have demonstrated the potential of CAIRT observations to quantify the injection of volcanic SO₂ and H₂SO₄ (Section 7.2.4 in the CAIRT RfA) and the detection and quantification of early geoengineering attempts by the deliberate injection of SO₂ into the stratosphere and their impacts on the stratospheric ozone layer (Section 7.4.4 in CAIRT RfMS). It would be highly beneficial to continue and extend this latter study to investigate the impact of these geoengineering attempts on stratospheric chemistry and circulation, and to show how CAIRT observations can detect and attribute these impacts. Any such studies should ideally put the CAIRT observations into context of observations from other observing systems anticipated to be available in the coming decades to demonstrate the added value of CAIRT observations and the possible synergies of different observations. This is a topic of high societal relevance.

The increased input of material into the middle atmosphere from a possible future increase in satellite launches and re-entries is another emerging topic with high societal relevance. While not being a “lower atmospheric coupling”, this topic closely relates to SO-4 from a scientific and societal point of view. A first study has been conducted as part of CAIRT Phase A demonstrating CAIRT’s potential to detect and possibly quantify aluminum oxide (Al₂O₃) in the atmosphere from satellite reentry under some future scenario with greatly enhanced number of spacecraft launches (and reentries) as part of expected upcoming satellite mega-constellations. It would be highly beneficial to expand these investigations to show the potential of CAIRT to detect and quantify the input of space-flight related material into the middle atmosphere and if possible its impact on composition, circulation and radiative balance. This should be compared with existing or other observational capacity to detect the impact of satellite reentry on atmospheric composition and dynamics to show the unique contribution of CAIRT.

SO-5 Resolve strong vertical gradients and fluxes of ozone and water vapour across the tropopause, facilitate the attribution of changes in middle atmospheric ozone, water vapour, and other constituents to changes in stratosphere-troposphere exchange, circulation, and chemistry, and improve our knowledge of the complex radiative-dynamic-chemical coupling governing our climate system.

Observations of ozone and water vapour in the upper troposphere and stratosphere are of relevance for monitoring and attributing climate change and ozone recovery, but also of direct practical relevance to improve weather forecasting. E.g., (Semane and Bonavita, 2025) have shown the importance of assimilation of UTLS water vapour from MLS observations into the ECMWF forecasting system for improving weather forecasts. A related study during CAIRT Phase A has investigated the importance of assimilation of MLS ozone in the ECMWF forecasting system. The observing system simulation experiments (OSSEs) with assimilation of CAIRT water and O₃ in comparison to MLS, conducted as part of CAIRT Phase 0 and Phase A (Section 7.4.5 of CAIRT RfMS; Errera et al., to be submitted, 2025), have quantitatively demonstrated the capabilities of CAIRT to constrain ozone and water vapour in the UTLS region. For ozone, results show that CAIRT data have a larger constrain than MLS in the upper troposphere. For water vapour, the constrain of CAIRT and MLS are similar. This is remarkable, as infra-red observations are more affected by clouds in the upper troposphere than microwave observations, which has been considered in these OSSEs. These results thus provide the required quantitative basis to relate the expected added value of CAIRT observations to NWP experiments (Semane and Bonavita, 2025). Nevertheless, it would be highly beneficial to conduct studies that show more directly the impact of CAIRT data in improving NWP, see below.

The need for continued/future limb observations to investigate stratospheric ozone recovery and related processes has repeatedly been highlighted (e.g. WMO et al., 2022). CAIRT observations would be highly

relevant in this respect by providing ozone over the whole middle atmosphere, together with key chemical species (in particular essentially the complete nitrogen family, important chlorine species such as ClONO₂, and many halogen containing source gases such as CFCs), sulfate aerosols and diagnostics of atmospheric circulation. These observations are directly relevant to monitor and attribute ozone recovery as mandated by the Parties of the Montreal Protocol. Emerging topics included in the assessment process of the Montreal Protocol are the impact of biomass burning emissions on stratospheric ozone, the impact of possible future geoengineering attempts, and the natural variability impacted by coupling with the upper atmosphere and solar variability. Existing performance estimates, together with recommended continued future studies on aerosols and geoengineering (as mentioned above), provide the required information to demonstrate the impact of CAIRT observations in the context of the Montreal Protocol.

AO-1 Support numerical weather, composition, and space weather forecasting, as well as climate services, re-analyses and aviation safety through assimilation of limb data (radiances, temperature, and relevant chemical trace constituents) from the upper troposphere to the lower thermosphere.

The importance of the middle atmosphere for numerical weather prediction has long been realized by most weather centers through the extension of numerical weather prediction models well into the mesosphere. Yet, few observations are available to constrain the models above the lower stratosphere. Recently (Semane and Bonavita, 2025) have demonstrated the benefits of assimilation of MLS water vapour limb observations into ECMWF's forecasting system to improve weather forecasts. Similar activities with the assimilation of MLS ozone observations into ECMWF's forecasting system have been started as part of CAIRT Phase A. Earlier studies conducted at Environment Canada as part of the PREMIER Phase A have already shown the added benefits of infra-red limb observations to better constrain ozone and water vapour in the UTLS for numerical weather prediction.

An important next step would be a study explicitly and quantitatively showing the forecast improvement – or error reduction – by the assimilation of CAIRT data. This should be done with established methodologies in close collaboration with ECMWF and/or national weather centers, e.g. as has been done for EPS-Sterna and EPS-Aeolus (The social and economic benefits of EPS-Aeolus and EPS-Sterna, Eumetsat, 2023). This could be based on simulated CAIRT Level-2 products temperature, water vapour and ozone, but ultimately should include the assimilation of simulated CAIRT Level-1 radiances, to exploit the full data content and as a move towards operational near-realtime data assimilation. This would require development (or at least adaption of existing) forward observation operators for the infra-red limb observations.

Artificial intelligence/machine learning (AI/ML) methods are currently a rapidly evolving field in NWP, which ultimately offer the possibility to provide weather forecasts directly from satellite observations, bypassing traditional data assimilation and numerical forecasting. This would offer new opportunities for the application of CAIRT data in weather prediction. Future studies investigating the feasibility of using infra-red limb data in AI/ML driven weather forecasts and quantifying the improvement in forecasts skills compared to the existing observing capabilities would thus be extremely beneficial.

Any work towards operational uptake of CAIRT data in numerical weather prediction (either via traditional data assimilation or through AI/ML methods) would have important additional benefits for the use and uptake of CAIRT data. This includes the use in climate re-analyses, which is much more probable if already methodologies for ingesting data in NWP exists, as well as early monitoring of data quality for cal/val activities.

Work towards assimilating CAIRT data in NWP may be extended to include assimilation of composition data for air quality and “chemical weather forecasting” such as done by CAMS. This may initially focus on ozone, but may well be extended to other relevant targets provided by CAIRT observations. In fact it may be part of

such as study to define which parameters would be most useful to improve CAMS forecasts and analyses. It has been noted (McNally et al., 2024) that AI/ML methods would provide a way to make use of atmospheric composition observations without the need to include explicitly the calculation of comprehensive atmospheric chemistry in forecasts models, which so far has limited the full uptake of atmospheric composition data. Impact studies that explore future possibilities of the use of CAIRT observations in NWP and composition forecasts, including AI/ML, show their impact on improved forecasts skill and their socio-economic benefits, and pave the way towards operational data use should have high priority.

Investigating the impact of assimilation of CAIRT observations in the MLT region could be seen as one aspect of the NWP and composition forecasts studies, but in practical terms would likely involve other partners, as most NWP models do not include the MLT region. See the discussion above for SO-3.

AO-2 Improve the retrieval of height-resolved and/or total column trace gases in the troposphere from nadir-observing systems through synergistic data fusion approaches and/or better quantification of trace gas amounts throughout the middle atmosphere.

Studies as part of PREMIER Phase A have already shown the potential to improve CH₄ emission inversions by infra-red limb observations. CAIRT Phase 0 studies have further investigated the impact of CAIRT limb observations in combination with IASI-NG and Sentinel 5 nadir observations to derive ozone concentrations in the troposphere. Updated future studies to show explicitly and quantitatively the impact of infra-red limb observations in improving height-resolved and/or total column trace gases in the troposphere, in particular for but not necessarily limited to CH₄, would be highly beneficial.

AO-3 Contribute to the representation, evaluation and validation of parameterized and resolved processes (e.g., wave drag, chemistry schemes, source/production terms, advection schemes, transport) in general circulation, chemistry-transport and chemistry-climate models.

Validation of models and guidance of further model development is an important overall goal of CAIRT's science objectives. For chemistry climate models, the SPARC CCM-Val activities, that have now evolved in APARC's Chemistry Climate Modelling Initiative (CCMI), have paved the way for a process-oriented validation of models. The SPARC CCMVal-2 Report (SPARC Report No. 5, 2010) as already stated clear requirements and recommendations for future vertically resolved observations in the stratosphere and upper troposphere: "Long-term vertically resolved data sets of constituent observations in the stratosphere are required to assess model behaviour and test model predictions. This includes ozone, but also other species that can be used to diagnose transport and chemistry. The current set of GCOS Essential Climate Variables is not sufficient for process-oriented validation of CCMs. More global vertically resolved observations are required, particularly in the UTLS. As CCMs evolve towards including tropospheric chemistry, lack of observations in this region will become a major limitation on model validation." Since the time of writing in 2010, the availability of vertically resolved data in the stratosphere and upper troposphere has not improved and these requirements are still valid. CAIRT's observational requirements and the assessed performance are aligned with these requirements and the expected impact of CAIRT data for model validation is well established.

As noted for SO-2 above, it may be beneficial if studies could demonstrate more quantitatively the impact of improved gravity-wave treatment on model performance or model forecasts. One step in this direction was performed as part of CAIRT Phase A with the WACCM-X model in different configurations (Sections 7.4.2 and 7.4.3 of CAIRT RfMS). Completing, possibly expanding, and publishing this study is highly recommended.

AO-4 Contribute to the understanding of the impacts of UTLS aerosol-water-ice cloud processes on outgoing longwave radiation, in conjunction with spectrally resolved radiance measurements across the entire infrared spectrum from nadir-observing systems along the same flight-track.

The impact of CAIRT observations to better understand and constrain the contribution of UTLS processes on outgoing longwave radiation has received relatively little attention in CAIRT Phase 0/A studies. These investigations are particularly relevant in conjunction with the EE9 FORUM mission. Future studies on these topics may quantify the synergies of FORUM's far infra-red and IASI mid-infrared nadir observations together with infra-red limb observations.

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